

Institute of Discourse Perspective

2nd International Conference

Syed Maududi's Thought: Dynamics & Impact

The phenomenal speaker presents this research in 2nd International Conference Syed Maududi's Thought: Dynamics &, held on 25-27 April 2025 at Al-Razi Hall, University of the Punjab, Lahore, Pakistan. The Conference Abstract is published on behalf of the decision of acceptance and approval of aforesaid Conference Organizing Committee.

Correspondence:

Hafiz Sajid Iqbal PhD, Chair of Organizing Committee, 2nd International Conference, Institute of discourse Perspectives, E.:
conferences.idp@gmail.com |
www.idpinstitute.com | +92 300 496 9385
| +92 333 4060783

Conference Secretariat: Fayaz Khan Jadoon, Institute of Islamic Perspective and Guidance, University of Management and Technology C-II, Johar Town, Lahore Pakistan. T.: +92 42 35212801-10, <https://www.umat.edu.pk>

Citation:

M.Tayyab Siddiqui, 2nd International Conference, Syed Maududi's Thought: Dynamics &, held in Al-Razi Hall, University of the Punjab, Lahore, Pakistan. Vol. 12 (2025). p. 21-22.

Competing Interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Additional information is available at the end of the article.

Conference Abstract

THE STRUGGLE BETWEEN ISLAM AND JAHILIYYAH IN THE THOUGHT OF MAULANA SYED ABUL A'LA MAUDUDI: AN INTELLECTUAL ANALYSIS

M.Tayyab Siddiqui

Mphil Scholar, Islamic Thought and Civilization at University of Management and Technology, Lahore, Punjab, Pakistan

Ethics approval and consent to participate: No ethical approval needed for this research work.

Consent for publication: Author is agreed to submit this abstract for publication in this research journal.

Availability of data and materials: The information and data collected and/ or incorporated in this study is included in this manuscript.

ABSTRACT

This paper looks at the ongoing struggle between Islam and Jahiliyyah (ignorance) through the ideas of Maulana Syed Abul A'la Maududi. Maududi argues that Jahiliyyah is not just something that existed in pre-Islamic times, but is a constant reality wherever human-made systems replace divine guidance. For him, Jahiliyyah appears whenever societies reject Islamic teachings and adopt secular, man-made ideologies, leading to moral and spiritual decline. The study draws primarily from Maududi's work "*Islami Nizam-e-Zindagi aur us ke Bunyadi Tasawwurat*", especially the chapter "Islam aur Jahiliyyah". It explores how Maududi defines Jahiliyyah and shows how it still exists in the modern world. Despite advancements in technology and society, modern secularism, materialism, and other ideologies continue to carry the essence of Jahiliyyah. Furthermore, the paper highlights Maududi's call for an Islamic revolution—one that replaces secular systems with a comprehensive way of life based on the sovereignty of Allah. Ultimately, this research aims to offer a clearer understanding of Maududi's vision of an Islamic order that confronts and overcomes the challenges of modern-day Jahiliyyah.

Keywords: Maulana Maududi, Jahiliyyah, Islamic political thought, Modern ignorance, Ideological conflict, Islamic system, Revivalism in Islam, Secularism vs Islam, Islamic governance

© 2025 The Author(s). This open access article is distributed under a Creative Commons Attribution (CC-BY) 4.0 license.

You are free to:

Share — copy and redistribute the material in any medium or format

Adapt — remix, transform, and build upon the material for any purpose, even commercially.

The licensor cannot revoke these freedoms as long as you follow the license terms.

Under the following terms:

Attribution — You must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made.

You may do so in any reasonable manner, but not in any way that suggests the licensor endorses you or your use.

No additional restrictions

You may not apply legal terms or technological measures that legally restrict others from doing anything the license permits